

AN ANALYSIS OF THE MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF DEGREE OF COMPARISON IN BLAAN LANGUAGE

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An Analysis of the Morphological Structure of Degree of Comparison in Blaan Language

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the morphological process in creating the adjective words in Blaan, particularly the structure from positive degree to their comparative and superlative degree of comparison. As a resource for Blaan, this study employed a qualitative discourse analysis research design with morphology as a level of analysis. Five native speakers of the Blaan language were chosen as volunteers in this study. They are explicitly confirming South Cotabato residents in Landan Polomolok, South Cotabato. The participants revealed that, as with the English Language, Blaan also has affixes that they attached to the Blaan Adjective to show its degree of comparison, such as "la Ali" for comparative degree and "to ti" for the superlative degree. "La Ali" is used when there is a comparison between two things, persons, or ideas, while "to ti" is used when comparing one thing, idea, or person among others. The direct impact of understanding affixes, affixation with morphological consciousness, the experimental language used, and beneficial procurement strategies that teachers may impart to students who use the Blaan language are among the conclusions drawn from this discussion of the significance of affix learning in language acquisition. The Blaan language does a fantastic job of developing common terms. This needs to be understood by native speakers themselves, particularly the younger ones. Native speakers need to be given language orientation and additional research on the Blaan Language in order to ease their fears of losing their mother tongue, as is the case with the Ligbok Language of a tribe in Capiz, Visayas, as described by Jessica Soho. Anyone who is eager to have a better understanding of the structure, formation, and laws of the Blaan language can readily examine the study's conclusions. Furthermore, future student researchers utilizing the same design for research will be able to refer to the study's methodology as a guide. Aspects of the Blaan language can be examined using other linguistic analysis levels, such as pragmatics, syntax, and semantics. This research serves as one of the cornerstones for developing educational resources and grammar manuals for Blaans.

Keywords: *English, morphological structure, degree of comparison, blaan tribal masters, Philippines*

Introduction

"Although it is true that language continues to evolve, it is sad to think that there are languages that are also slowly dying with the passage of time. The language of a tribe in the town of Tapaz in Capiz, the sign is said to be several thousand years old. But now, it is said to be gradually disappearing. In this webexclusive, meet Lola Feliza, who is believed to be the oldest local who still speaks "Ligbok," a language that is considered a "dying language", an episode of Kapuso Mo Jessica Soho last August 28, 2016."

I conducted this study related to the Kapuso Mo Jessica Soho episode mentioned above. It focuses on a particular component of speech used by our Blaan siblings. It concentrated on the Blaan adjective and its three degrees of comparison: superlative, comparative, and positive. Similar to the tribe that was featured in the KMJS episode, our Blaan tribal elders fear that their language will be lost as a result of various factors that influence how their language is used, such as the younger generation's reluctance to speak in public with people from different cultures for fear of being judged because Blaan people are seen as having low status in the community.

According to Akmajian et al. (2017), all languages give means of expression for asking questions, transmitting messages, making assertions, and the like. Nothing in one word could be transferred into any other language. Discovering the minor meaningful units of sentences or utterances is the subject matter of the science known as morphology. Ferrara and Hodge (2018) stated that the production of words in the language is studied in linguistics, including a discussion of and description of word formation - as inflection, derivation, and compounding.

In addition, Fortes (2022) explicitly stated that the Philippine-type linguistic documentation, the revival of languages and initiatives to do so have grown when the MTBMLE was implemented for the primary grades. Variations in language, including the Southern Bisakol, in Sorsogon are commonly utilized but not researched as well by native speakers. Of the grammatical classifications verbs and nouns are examined. They're content terms, which are typically presented in the elementary school grades. Employing Payne's descriptive analysis, morphosyntax, and Nolasco's stem-based theory used structural analysis to examine the transcription assembled in the Bisakol corpus. Notable results indicate that verbs and nouns are derived types possessing distinct morphemes that could anchored to the stem or the root, respectively. The Bisakol affixes are somewhat conditioned and limitations in the language setting. Thus, Bisakol morphemes—in particular, their affixes, which have numerous uses in every an addendum with a significance that could change the root's semantics may alter the idea the entire new form's category.

This study by Trocio et al. (2023) examined the flavor (oral lore) of the Blaan indigenous peoples (IPs) in the Philippines, namely in General Santos, Sarangani, and South Cotabato. It used qualitative-descriptive approaches to explore patterns of traditional beliefs in myths, legends, and folktales as repeated by Blaan ancestors. Using Thompson's MotifIndex Theory, recurrent themes in a few Blaan

folktales were codified. Family ties, household connections, and other Blaan cultural themes are prevalent in the flalok labor, tribal conflicts, sporting events, catching animals, and agricultural cultivation. The study added to the ongoing improvement of Filipino Studies and defines Mindanao Studies as a significant component of that effort. In order to comprehend how the lives and works of Mindanaoan Tri-people (IPs, Bangsamoro, and Christian settlers) preserve broader Filipino cultural viewpoints, it can serve as a reference for academics, researchers, and cultural workers. In particular, it offers more welcoming beginning points for timeless cultural themes to be included in the broader awareness of culture mirrored in Philippine dance, music, theater, film, and other artistic mediums.

Because of how other tribes perceive their tribe, I have firsthand experience with the previously indicated reason why the younger generation is reluctant to use their language or identify as Blaan. This could be the origin of the tribal chiefs of the Blaan tribe's concern of losing their language, similar to what happened to the language used in the Kapuso Mo Jessica Soho.

The study of morphology is vital because it helps students comprehend the composition and structure of words, which makes it imperative. When studying language acquisition and linguistic change, students can benefit from having a solid foundation in morphemic analysis. Even educators working in disciplines like linguistics, vocabulary development, and language processing can benefit from morphological analysis. Teachers and students can advance other critical learning abilities as they get more knowledge about morphemic analysis.

Methodology

The systematic investigation of social phenomena in unstructured environments is known as qualitative research. These phenomena may include but are not limited to how people perceive different aspects of their lives, how people behave individually or in groups, how businesses run, and how interactions affect interpersonal relationships. The researcher is the primary data-gathering tool in qualitative research. The researcher looks at what happens, why things happen, and what those things signify to the persons under study. This study employed a qualitative discourse analysis research design with morphology as a level of analysis.

According to Tenny et al. (2022), qualitative research looks at actual issues and offers a more in-depth understanding. Qualitative research aids in generating hypotheses and further investigating and interpreting quantitative data instead of gathering numerical data points or introducing treatments as in quantitative research. Qualitative research collects the views, behaviors, and experiences of people. Rather than addressing how many or how much, it addresses hows and whys. It may be set up as a stand-alone study using only qualitative data, or it may be a component of a mixed-methods study using both qualitative and quantitative data review to introduce the readers to some basic concepts, definitions, terminology, and application of qualitative research (Brennan et al., 2022).

Discourse analysis is a technique that looks at any important semiotic event—spoken, written, or in the language used. Linguistics, a discipline concerned with creating and constructing words, was used to conduct this discourse analysis. In this paper, the morphological process that produced Blaan adjectives with degrees ranging from positive to comparative to superlative was specifically investigated utilizing morphology at an analytical level. This device examined the lingua franca's structure using a researcher's collection of native speakers' usage of the language that was then subjected to methodical examination (Berez-Kroeker et al., 2018).

In addition, discourse analysis is the study and examination of language usage. Because discourse analysis has so many applications, we have divided the methodologies into three groupings. Additionally, we have given examples of how each method might be used to research a specific subject—patient-doctor communication about diabetes management, in this case. Discourse analysts can access extensive data sources independent of their chosen methodology, such as published literature, media, web-based resources, transcripts from focus groups, interviews, and conversation samples (Mulvenna et al., 2017).

Also, discourse analysis focuses on examining and analyzing how language is used. Due to the term's broad usage, we have categorized discourse analysis techniques into three clusters and shown how each could be applied to examine a particular domain, doctor-patient communication regarding diabetes care. Regardless of methodology, the discourse analyst has access to numerous data sources, such as transcripts of interviews, focus groups, conversation samples, published literature, media, and web-based materials.

Similarly, discourse analysis is steadily growing in popularity in family practice. Discourse analysis, which employs precise procedures and approaches, can provide profound insight into the intricate realm of family practice. However, what exactly do we mean, and how is "discourse analysis" carried out? This paper's first section, which seeks to address this query, focuses on some fundamental theoretical notions and ideas while drawing from primary care-related studies to give readers a comprehension of the characteristics of discourse analysis and the various available methodologies. In the second section of this essay, we examine discourse analysis techniques, consider popular arguments, and use data from a recent study in family practice. In order to wrap things up, we demonstrate how discursive studies could give family practice research a "new" methodological component.

Furthermore, discourse analysis studies social life as understood through analyzing language in its broadest sense (including face-to-face conversation, non-verbal interaction, images, symbols, and documents). It provides methods for examining meaning, whether in speech or culture. They enquire about the social lifelike?" What are the ramifications for people and society?"

The procedure for conducting discourse analysis is not predetermined. A few practical techniques can help researchers, as there are other qualitative methods. Background reading is crucial in the research process because it clarifies the research topics and shows how

theoretical concepts and techniques.

The research's primary objective determines the data type that will be acquired. Data may be gathered from various sources to understand the events' circumstances. Data can be "researcher-created" (such as from interviews or field notes) or "naturally occurring" (such as from published materials or conversation recordings).

In qualitative research, this looks at the theory of critical discourse analysis. The analysis framework examines texts, relationships, and social norms at the institutional, cultural, and regional levels. It aims to make clear the politics and arguments in favor of and against particular research designs, claims, or moral principles. Its basis is the requirement for using critical discourse analysis to describe, interpret, analyze, and critique social life as it is portrayed in literature. According to the essay, texts offer a range of meanings, concepts, and worldviews that position and construct individuals. Texts also assist human subjects in forming social contacts and relationships throughout daily life and making sense of their environment (Armayanti, 2019).

By illuminating how scholars might apply critical theory to identify pertinent empirical research strategies and to increase the analytical, critical, and occasionally liberating power of data collection and interpretation, James (2020) claims that theory and educational research help to bridge the gap between traditional theories. Tracey and Morrow (2017) added that, "Theory stifles educators' creativity as researchers, legislators, and educators by limiting how they can approach issues in the classroom."

The Philippines has two official languages: English and Filipino (Tagalog). Beginning in kindergarten, English is taught in schools and utilized as a medium of instruction. The usage of Tagalog in academia has been criticized for discriminating against indigenous and regional languages other than Tagalog, which are not typically used in higher education and have thus not been allowed to grow as academic languages because it was initially imposed by Western colonialism. DepEd Order No. 16, series of 2012, sometimes referred to as the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) order, was released by the Filipino Department of Education in 2012. The MTB-MLE policy was recently implemented in public schools, but it has already encountered significant issues that question its effectiveness. One of these is the need for more teaching resources because most textbooks on the market are published in either Filipino or English. The potential of oral traditions as teaching aids in elementary education is examined in this essay. Folklorists have worked hard to gather, document, and publish folk epics, myths, legends, and stories. The recording and disseminating of information in the original languages or versions used by native informants from indigenous groups is a crucial component of this research (Jorolan-Quintero, 2018).

The use of theory in educational research is supported by five different types of arguments, according to Malmi (2020): i) argument by analogy, which, while providing a valuable example for educational research, does not imply that theory must be equally helpful when transferring from one subject to another; ii) reorganization of experience, which in this case is a more significant approach to thinking about the role of theory in addressing the question of determining the necessity of theory in a subject matter; iii) the absurdity of bare empiricism; iv) Deweyan problem solving, which describes inquiry as the transformation of an uncertain a scenario when a problem is presented and then resolved to create a single, unified problem, and v) the understanding of complexity (one of the main goals of theory is to demonstrate how, upon closer inspection, seemingly straightforward subjects of empirical study turn out to be complicated).

As stated by Armayanti (2019), no fact, investigation, or conclusion can be devoid of theory. The inquiry pertains to one's comprehension of the theory and whether or not it is being applied critically. Any education-related occurrence must be interpreted within the larger political, social, and economic frameworks. One should look for theories that draw linkages in these areas. Theories may aid in understanding the people, situations, and structures under investigation and be used to change them. One should include theory into the logic of their study and use it to further their research, as opposed to only employing it to support claims.

In his research, Mullet (2018) asserts that understanding pressing societal issues is the main driving force behind and focus of critical discourse analysis. Power and justice concerns, as well as how the economy, race, class, gender, religion, education, and sexual orientation shape, reproduce or alter social systems, are all central to critical theories. Consequently, a thorough explanation of the relationships among text, speech, society, and culture is required. Teaching and learning policies can be better understood by examining the language, text genres, and social issues prevalent in the community.

Likewise, Elliott (2018) claimed that critical discourse analysis emphasizes the value of interdisciplinary study to thoroughly understand language's role in creating and sharing knowledge inside the framework of social organizations. Critical discourse analysis examines the underlying origins and effects of problems over an extended period.

Not to mention, Bax (2018) emphasized that critical discourse analysis compels us to stop thinking of language as abstract and start thinking of it as having meaning within a particular historical, social, and political context. Thus, critical discourse analysis is used to study real-world, often extended instances of social interaction that predominantly take on linguistic shape (Baker & Saldanha, 2019).

This qualitative investigation is explicitly affected by a substantial ethical dilemma. Most of these concerns can be attributed to the study's methodology. The relevant ethical obstacles in this research field were the challenges of conducting an acceptable study and maintaining confidentiality and anonymity. The conditions for ethical consideration set forth by the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee were followed in this study.

Results and Discussion

Research Question No. 1: How is the degree of comparison of the common adjective words in the Blaan language being formed?

Researchers conduct in-depth, unstructured interviews to gather information and create a complete picture of the interviewee's situation or point of view. Three primary techniques for conducting qualitative interviews were identified by Braun and Clarke (2022): the standardized open-ended interview, the general interview guide approach, and the informal conversational interview.

Tables 1 and 2 present Blaan Adjectives in Comparative Degree and Superlative Degree respectively.

The succeeding page's Table 1 displays the comparative degree of Blaan adjectives. "La ali" is the base form of the Blaan adjective, which now serves the additional purpose of comparing two items, people, or concepts when "la ali" is attached to them. This is how two things are compared when using the Blaan Adjectives.

The verb affix adaptation of the prefixes a, ay, and ha in the Cebuano language gave rise to the Verb Affix Adaptation Theory, according to Cantular's Morphological Borrowing (2018): A Linguistic Ethnographic Study of Cagay-anon Sebuano Verb Affix Adaptation. The three Higaonon suffixes were adapted into the standard Cebuano language of the Cagay-anon through both extralinguistic and intralinguistic processes, according to the Verb Affix Adaptation Theory and the Linguist Adaptation Theory. This suggests that affixes have an impact on the fundamental structures of words when they are linked to them.

When expressing comparative degree in Blaan sentences, the affixes and the Blaan-based form of adjectives appear before the other sentence components. However, the subject comes before the comparative degree adjective in English sentences. These adjectives are frequently seen in sentences.

These will combine the Blaan Adjective's bare form with "la Ali" to generate the Blaan adjectives that are in a comparative degree. However, it adds "er" or the word "more" to make its comparative degree in English sentences.

The comparative markers "beg" (SBL) or "bég" (TBL) are used to indicate the comparative degree of adjectives, and are positioned before an adjective (beg/bég + adj.). When using KBL, an adjective is positioned before the comparative marker "=malù" (malù + adj.). When using CBL, an adjective comes before the comparative marker "too" (too + adj.). Additionally, SBL employs the superlative degree marker "too/too ti/beg ti" to indicate the superlative degree of adjectives, and it places these markers before an adjective (too/too ti/beg ti + adj.). In KBL, an adjective is positioned before the superlative markers "too/tay/too ti/tay ti" (too/tay/too ti/tay ti + adj.). The superlative marker "too" is positioned before an adjective in TBL (too + adj.).

A language's lexicon is a catalog of everything that is said to exist in the language; in technical words, morphology is the study of a word's internal structure (as quoted in Aronoff & Anshen, 2017). These two linguistic features are intimately related because they both result in words. Jensen and Stong-Jensen (cited in Aronoff & Anshen, 2017) assert that morphology and the lexicon are related because some linguists maintain that morphology is "in the lexicon." This study looks at the lexical variants of the significant lexical categories, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and nouns in the sociolinguistic contexts of SBL, KBL, CBL, and TBL.

In technical terms, morphology is the study of a word's internal structure; lexicons are lists of all the things that are said to exist in a language. Because they both lead to words, these two linguistic characteristics are closely connected. The lexical variants of the major lexical categories, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and nouns in the sociolinguistic contexts of SBL, KBL, CBL, and TBL are examined in this study. They claimed that morphology and the lexicon are related because some linguists maintain that morphology is "in the lexicon."

Table 1: *Blaan adjectives in comparative degree*

La ali (Blaan Comparative Degree)		
Sample Sentence	Blaan Sentence	English Translation
Adjective: mlanêb (clean)		
Sentence 1	La ali mlanêb i gumnê ani di gumne Maya.	Maya's house is cleaner than this.
Sentence 2	La ali mlanêb i fligo gu ni di fligo Amera.	Amera's plate is cleaner than mine.
Sentence 3	La ali mlaneb I baweham di baweham.	Your face is cleaner than her.
Adjective: magsik/magagsik (dirty)		
Sentence 1	La ali magsik i tnalu Jun di kene Jan.	Jan's hand is dirtier than Jun.
Sentence 2	La ali magsik nayê i klubengam di klubeng dareme.	Others eyebrow looks dirtier than yours.
Sentence 3	La ali magsik i gumile am di gumile an.	His bed is dirtier than yours.
Adjective: fye (good)		
Sentence 1	La ali ti fye i balu gu ni di kafid gu.	My Twin's attitude is better mine.
Sentence 2	La ali ti fye i nimo am bola di nimo Lowla.	Lowla's handmade ball is better than yours.
Sentence 3	La ali ti fye fandam i dad lagi lamnok di dad libun lamnok .	Young girls think better than young boys.
Adjective: sasê (bad)		
Sentence 1	La ali an sasê arat i Tami gu di kene Ma.	My Father's character is worse than grandfather.
Sentence 2	La ali sasê balu nga Bie di kene Bob.	Bob's attitude is worse than Young Bie.
Sentence 3	La ali sasê nayê i bawêham di kanen.	Her face looks worse than yours.

Adjective: fnò (full)		
Sentence 1	La ali ti fno utăn i sawatan gu di kanen.	His bowl of viand is fuller than mine.
Sentence 2	La ali ti fno gatas' i basô I nga ani di ngaam.	This child's glass of milk is fuller that your child.
Sentence 3	La ali ti fno knaan i fligom di fligo gu.	My plate of rice is fuller than yours.
Adjective: ndè lam (empty)		
Sentence 1	La ali ndè lam yeel i basô Dan di kene Billy.	Billy's glass of water is emptier than Dan.
Sentence 2	La ali ndè lam msè i gu fkaha gu di gufkaham.	Your rice dispenser is emptier than mine.
Sentence 3	La ali ndè lam yeel i kabong la di kabong mi.	Our bamboo water pitcher is emptier than them.

The superlative degree of comparison of Blaan Adjectives is displayed in Table 2 on the preceding page. Using the Blaan Adjectives, they used "too ti" to contrast an item, a person, or an idea. The fundamental form of the Blaan adjective now serves the additional purpose of comparing anything or everything to everyone. Morphological processes involve using morphological knowledge to change root words and affixes into grammatically sound terms. Speakers dissect the root words of multimorphemic words into their constituent parts. Multimorphemic forms are produced by appending grammatical morphemes to the base words, such as suffixes. According to growing research, morphological skills may also be necessary for reading acquisition in addition to phonological, orthographic, and vocabulary skills (Levesque et al., 2021).

In English sentences, the subject comes before the adjective, which indicates a superlative degree; these words are frequently inserted between sentences, whereas in Blaan sentences, affixes and the adjective's Blaan-based form occur before the other sentence components.

In forming the Blaan adjectives in the superlative degree, they will have the "too ti" plus the primary form of a Blaan Adjective. On the other hand, in English sentences, it forms its superlative degree by adding "iest" and or the word "most."

The comparative degree of an adjective is indicated by the comparative markers "beg" (SBL) or "bég" (TBL), which are placed prior to the adjective (beg/bég + adj.). An adjective comes before the comparative marker "=malù" (malù + adj.) when employing KBL. When utilizing CBL, the comparative marker "too" is preceded by an adjective (too + adj.). SBL also indicates the superlative degree of adjectives by using the superlative degree markers "too/too ti/beg ti," which are positioned before an adjective (too/too ti/beg ti + adj.). The superlative markers "too/tay/too ti/tay ti" (too/tay/too ti/tay ti + adj.) are preceded by an adjective in KBL. In TBL (too + adj.), the superlative marker "too" comes before an adjective.

In technical terms, morphology is the study of a word's internal structure, and a language's lexicon is a list of all the things that are said to exist in the language (as quoted in Aronoff & Anshen, 2017). Since both linguistic characteristics create words, they are closely related. According to Jensen and Stong-Jensen (quoted in Aronoff & Anshen, 2017), morphology and the lexicon are interconnected since some linguists claim that morphology is "in the lexicon." In the sociolinguistic contexts of SBL, KBL, CBL, and TBL, the lexical variants on the significant lexical categories—nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs—are examined in this study.

All of the things that are supposedly present in a language are listed in its lexicon; morphology, to put it technically, is the study of a word's underlying structure. Due to their shared ability to produce words, these two linguistic traits are closely related. This research examines the lexical variants of the major lexical categories, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and nouns in the sociolinguistic contexts of SBL, KBL, CBL, and TBL. They claimed that morphology and the lexicon are related because some linguists maintain that morphology is "in the lexicon."

Table 2: *Blaan adjectives in Superlative Degree*

Too ti (Blaan Superlative Degree)		
Adjective: mlanêb (clean)		
<i>Sample Sentence</i>	<i>Blaan Sentence</i>	<i>English Translation</i>
Sentence 1	Too ti mlanêb i gumnê Carla.	Carla's house is the cleanest.
Sentence 2	Too ti mlanêb I fligo Sarah.	Sarah's plate is the cleanest.
Sentence 3	Too ti mlanêb i bawêh gu di krêên.	My face is the cleanest of all.
Adjective: magsik/magagsik (dirty)		
Sentence 1	Too ti magsik i tnalu Alen di krêên.	Alen's hand is the dirtiest of all.
Sentence 2	Too ti magsik nayê i klubeng Mona.	Mona's eyebrow looks dirtiest.
Sentence 3	Too ti magsik i gumile guru.	My bed is the dirtiest.
Adjective: fye (good)		
Sentence 1	Too ti fye balu i twali gu lagi di krêê.	My younger brother has the best attitude of all.
Sentence 2	Too ti fye i bola' nimo Alex di krêên.	Alex handmade ball is the best of all.
Sentence 3	Too ti fye fandam i dad tua to.	Old people think best.
Adjective: sasê (bad)		
Sentence 1	Too ti sasê arat i Fo gu.	My Grandmother's character is worst.
Sentence 2	Too ti sasê balu Dalia di krêê saflanek.	Dalia's attitude is the worst among siblings.
Sentence 3	Too ti sasê nayê bawê Dina kanen.	Dina's face looks worst.
Adjective: fnò (full)		
Sentence 1	Too ti fno utăn i sawatan Lino.	Lino's bowl of viand is the fullest.

Sentence 2	Too ti fno gatas i basô i nga Linda.	Linda's child's glass of milk is the fullest.
Sentence 3	Too ti fno knaan i fligo Carla.	Carla's plate has the fullest rice.
Adjective: ndè lam (empty)		
Sentence 1	Too ti ndè lam yeel i basô am.	Your glass of water is the emptiest.
Sentence 2	Too ti ndè lam msè i gu fkah mi msó.	Our rice dispenser is the emptiest.
Sentence 3	Too ti ndè lam yeel i kabong Jona.	Jona's bamboo water pitcher is the emptiest.

Conclusion

As this study focused on the formation of Blaan Adjectives from based form to the comparative degree to its superlative degree, which is being formed this way:

From the based form, "la Ali" was added to form the based form of the Blaan Adjective to a comparative degree. Given the example by Participant No. 3, she used the Blaan Adjective "bong," which means big. She added "la ali" to "bong" to make it "la ali bong," which means more prominent in English.

On the other hand, Participant No. 1 explained that to show superlative degree using the Blaan Adjective, all you need to do is to affix "too ti" to the based form of the Blaan Adjective. For example, the Blaan Adjective "mlayef" means light (weight) in English. He said, "Too ti mlayef i set bol anak." Which means A chicken feather is the lightest." in English.

In this regard, the teachers, students, parents, and community members, in general, would benefit significantly from this qualitative research study in discourse analysis because it focuses on a morphological analysis of the structure of the adjective words used in Blaan. This would help them better understand how words in Blaan are formed, specifically in forming the degree of comparison of Blaan Adjectives.

In particular, teachers might use this as a reference when teaching language-related courses. This study could undoubtedly be helpful to the teachers in our current educational system, which currently uses mother-tongue-based learning. If they are not native speakers, they can also use this as a guide for learning the Blaan language.

Since the tribal elders are concerned about the possibility of their language being lost gradually as a result of the effects of diverse cultures within the community, students, in addition to teachers, can use this as a reference when studying the Blaan language, whether it is their mother tongue or not. Several younger Blaans had already grown far from their language as adults. They will benefit from this study in that regard.

This study will guide the parents in enabling their youngsters to grasp better and study the language that serves as their mother tongue. Also, this research will aid them in expanding their expertise, particularly about the degree of comparability in Blaan Adjectives.

As was already mentioned, the tribal elders in the Barangay Landan community are concerned about losing the language they have worked so hard to maintain for so many years, as they witnessed with the Ligbok language featured in Jessica Soho. Young native Blaan speakers are exposed to numerous cultures and languages. In addition, some Blaan youth today seem embarrassed by their heritage. When the researcher explained to the participants what the study would be about, they immediately expressed excitement. They even routinely requested updates on the interview schedule communicated to them by the researcher. The tribe leaders regard this study as a way to aid them in preserving their culture, particularly their language, for many years to come. They requested a copy of this research because they intended to use it to educate their children, specifically on the Blaan adjective.

After completing this study, I felt moved by the awareness of how crucial the preservation of the Blaan people's culture and language is, especially to the tribe masters. Initially, this is just a study to supplement my prior understanding of the language and give me something to work toward towards my master's degree. However, as time passed and I gave in to the participant interviews, my love and desire to complete my work increased. I witnessed the tribe elders' seriousness in trying to find means of preserving their language in the face of changes both inside and outside of their society. The joy I witnessed in the eyes of my subjects stoked my desire to not only complete my research but also to find a way to alleviate their dread of language death.

This study served as a link between me and the language preservation objective, as well as my participants. I dedicate this study to the entire new Blaan generation, especially to my volunteers who generously donated their time to provide me with the data I needed for this research. In particular, I spoke with one of my participants about my study and his desire for a copy even during our most recent conversation, which took place while he was in the hospital. I give him this study, and I hope that when it is all said and done, his soul will be content.

When affixes and roots are provided in a precise order, young grammar learners come across terms that they were previously unfamiliar with. The results demonstrated that students taught about roots and affixes performed better than those who had to study affixation as a component of morphological awareness. Morphological awareness is the ability to comprehend the meaning of morphemes in the context of words and how they are combined. The ability to build morphological structures promotes the expansion of one's vocabulary within a suitable linguistic context.

The results of this study indicate that, like English speakers, Blaan also uses the affixation process to demonstrate the degree of

similarity in their use of adjectives. Furthermore, affixes like "la Ali," which indicates comparative degree, and "to it," which indicates superlative degree, are affixed to corresponding adjectives to construct the degree of comparison.

The Landan, Polomolok, South Cotabato Blaan Tribal Masters. Mindanao people are worried that the changes occurring in their diverse community could lead to the eventual extinction of their language. Some native speakers, including Bisaya and Long, would rather converse in languages other than their own out of fear of prejudice from others.

The development of everyday terms in the Blaan Language is done superbly. The native speakers themselves must understand this, especially the younger ones. In order to allay their concern of losing their mother tongue, as what is happening with the Ligbok Language of a tribe living in Capiz, Visayas, which was documented by Jessica Soho, language orientation and more research regarding the Blaan Language must be provided to the native speakers.

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